

History of Hadrah Tradition as A Medium of Communication and Social Interaction in Maluku

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Abstract

The Hadrah tradition is a one-of-a-kind ceremony observed by the Maluku people during religious festivals. In Hadrah, the Hadrah tradition can be defined as the community making friends while dancing and shouting prayers to the Prophet Muhammad to the accompaniment of music (tambourine). The Hadrah tradition is a method of acculturation and blending of Islam and Maluku's indigenous culture. As such, this study will discuss how the Hadrah tradition facilitates dialogue across varied communities and serves as a means of resolving horizontal problems amongst communities in Maluku. The descriptive qualitative method was employed in the investigation. The findings of the study of the Hadrah tradition cannot be divorced from the history of Islam's introduction into Maluku, specifically through Arab, Indian, and Chinese traders who came to trade while preaching Islam. During Islamic festivals, the Hadrah ritual is a unique custom followed by the community in which residents stroll around the village making acquaintances while the village dances to the accompaniment of chanting prayers to the Prophet Muhammad, his closest companion and confidant. Finally, the Hadrah tradition's emphasis on cohesion, cohesiveness, and unity will result in the formation of a high-quality society that values cohesion and avoids conflict.

Keywords: *Tradition, Hadrah, Local Culture, Islam, Communication, Social Interaction.*

INTRODUCTION

Maluku was known as a spice producer from the beginning of the 15th century, and foreign traders came to Maluku in search of cloves and nutmeg. They came from all throughout Asia, from Arabs to Gujaratis to Chinese to Javanese and Malay Muslims (Pattikayhatu, 2012). Because kings and nobles were involved in trading operations, Islamization through this trade was extremely beneficial. Those involved in Islamic education and outreach, as well as traders, do business with the locals. Commerce routes and shipping and trade routes spread and expanded Islam in Indonesia (Syafrizal, 2015).

Because Muslim traders enjoyed a higher social position than most indigenous due to their financial success, local women, particularly noble daughters, were drawn to marry these men. They were Muslim before they were married (Murod, 2011). As a result of bearing children, they began colonizing Muslim communities, territories, and kingdoms all over the world. When these Arabs married local women, they formed a nucleus of the Muslim society that included both immigrants and locals. Members of this Muslim community also participate in outreach initiatives aimed at educating others about Islam (Wekke, 2014).

The archipelago's indigenous peoples had a nomadic lifestyle and a dynamic belief system before they were influenced by outsiders. In Maluku Islands, the impact of animism and dynamism began to fade after the arrival and spread of Islam (Thalib, 2012). This region was first exposed to Islamic teachings by Arab businessmen and missionaries, who came to trade and spread the religion's ideals (Leirissa & Latuconsina, 1999).

While the Arab community's method of promoting Islam doesn't always remove society from its culture, the community's habits do propagate religion. The religious development in the Maluku Islands is particularly vibrant because this adaptation strategy does not pit religion against culture; rather, it works through culture to spread Islam in a way that benefits both (Ulum, 2014). When it comes to cultural integration, Hadrah is one of the most popular customs. In the Maluku islands, the Hadrah tradition plays an important role in establishing social ties among various tribes and cultures. Inter-community integration during the Hadrah procedure (Hasni et al., 2017).

The Hadrah tradition is a culture with meaning and value of solidarity for the community. The Hadrah tradition is found throughout the archipelago. This tradition is carried out at the time of Eid al-Fitr and Eid al-Adha. The Hadrah tradition in Maluku is significant in creating a peaceful society. The community assembled in the mosque's courtyard, and the Hadrah

tradition began to encircle the hamlet and reassemble in the mosque's courtyard. After walking around the village, we continued with a prayer of thanksgiving, and each eye of the house brought alkadar to the mosque. The Hadrah tradition is finished, followed by congratulating and forgiving each other (Lestari, 2020).

Hadrah is one of the Islamic arts. This Hadrah is carried out by community leaders who are proficient in performing Hadrah and understand the teachings of Islam because all the pronunciations and poems come from the values of pure Islamic teachings (Umam, 2020). The terms Hadrah and "Hadi" come from the same Arabic language, which means "Present" or hadlir. Haldir in question is how we, as servants of God, can feel the presence of God within us. Men usually play this Hadrah culture with 4 tambourine beaters, then 6 dancers, and the community, both young and old, always watch and encourage Hadrah players. The Hadrah culture, in addition to functioning as art, also has a function as a medium of da'wah and praises the name of Allah and the Messenger of Allah as messengers of Allah (Tindarika & Ramadhan, 2021).

It is important here to see Hadrah in the context of human relations and to see it further as communication with an ethical perspective, including encouraging efforts to build relationships. The primary assumption is that the moral philosophy that applies in a society always has a historical and cultural basis in the local context (Marjito & Juniardi, 2021). In general, the Hadrah tradition is a tradition that exists in the community in creating togetherness and harmony between the community (Arifianto et al., 2018). Besides this, the Hadrah tradition is expected to overcome various inter-tribal conflicts that occur among the people in the Maluku islands.

Based on this, the authors are interested in researching implementing the Hadrah tradition in Maluku as a means of interaction, communication, and the resolution of social conflicts in society. It is hoped that this research will contribute to scientific development and become a scientific reference to add to the intellectual treasures of the academic community so that this research can be used as material to formulate a theory. Besides, for practical purposes, it is hoped that this research can be a valuable input to further increase self-awareness in the community of the importance of the Hadrah tradition as a medium of communication and conflict resolution in society.

METHOD

Specifically, the qualitative approach used in this study is a research method that aims to describe incomplete and in-depth social reality as well as various phenomena that occur in the community that is being studied, in order to depict the characteristics, characters, characteristics, and models of these phenomena (Gunawan, 2013). This research approach employs descriptive qualitative research, which is a systematic account of a particular occurrence that is factually and accurately about the things that occur. In qualitative research, the researcher's presence serves as both an instrument and a data collector, depending on the type of research being conducted. Because of the presence of researchers and data collectors, the presence of researchers is required (Somantri, 2005).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Entry of Islam into the Archipelago

In Indonesia, the advent of Islam did not take place at the same time in different regions. Political and socio-cultural contexts were also distinct in each of the kingdoms they visited. Indonesia's conversion to Islam generated a wide range of views. Figures like these, who had firsthand knowledge of Indonesia's integration and rapid growth of Islamic beliefs, were among those who voiced their concerns. Western (European) researchers who came to Indonesia on assignments or were employed by the government were among those who conducted research on Islam's arrival into Indonesia:

1. The latest Arab news. Arab traders that conduct business with Indonesians are aware of this development. Trade routes in western Indonesia, including the Malacca Strait, were controlled by the Srivijaya monarchy (7th century AD). The existence of Arab traders for the Srivijaya monarchy, such as Zabak, Zabay, or Scribus, proves the link between Arab traders and the Srivijaya kingdom. Most Islamic luminaries in Indonesia, such as Hamka and Abdullah bin Nuh, have articulated this sentiment in their writings, including Sheikh Muhammad Naquib Al-Attas (1972). He claims that the belief that Islam originated in India is a sort of propaganda, and that the pure Islam that arrived in Southeast Asia is not the same as the pure Islam that originated in India (Bachtiar, 2018).
2. News from Europe Marcopolo relayed this information in 1292 AD. When he returned by sea from China to Europe, he was the first person to set foot in Indonesia. He was assigned by the Chinese emperor to deliver his daughter to the Roman

emperor; on this journey, he made a stop in northern Sumatra. He established an Islamic monarchy in this region, termed the Ocean kingdom with its capital at Pasai (Permana, 2015).

3. India News. According to this report, Gujarati traders had a critical role in the spread of Islam and Islamic culture throughout Indonesia. This is because, in addition to business, they actively engage in spreading Islamic religious and cultural values throughout the world, particularly among the coastal populations. After the year 1883 AD, this theory was first put forth as an idea. C. Snouch Hurgronje brought it (2006).
4. Chinese News. Ma Huan, a writer who followed Admiral Cheng-ho's voyage, passed on this information. As far back as 1400, he wrote, there were Muslim merchants living along the north shore of Java Island. Arab traders dominated East-West trade between the 7th and 8th century AD and promoted Islam across the archipelago, T.W. Arnold claimed. A Muslim Arab town on the Sumatran coast was allegedly led by an Arab trader in the 7th century AD, according to Chinese accounts (Binarto, 2020).
5. Domestic Sources. The rise of Islam in Indonesia can be explained by sources within the country. Discovering a stone in Learn, for example (Gresik). Some of the inscription on the inscribed stone has been broken, and it is written in Arabic. Fatimah Binti Maimun is shown in the stone (1028). First of all, the tomb of Sultan Malikul Saleh, who died in the month of Ramadan in the year 676 H or 1297 AD, in North Sumatra. Secondly Lastly, Jirat Makan imported from Gujarat the tomb of Sheikh Maulana Malik Ibrahim, who died in 1419 AD and included Arabic literature.

There were no violent clashes when Islam arrived in Indonesia and spread to its nobles and the ordinary population. Islamization has been place through six distinct routes (Dalimunthe, 2016):

1. Channels of Trade in Indonesia's early beginnings, trade was one of the means of Islamization. From the 7th to the 16th century, Muslim traders (Arabic, Persian, and Indian) in Indonesia had a significant impact on trade with countries in Asia's west, southeast, and east. It was extremely advantageous to use trade as a conduit for Islamization. Trade between Indonesians and foreigners is strengthened by this. It is explained here that Islamization through trade channels was accelerated by several kingdoms' political situations and conditions. The coastal dukes were trying to escape from the power of the main domain, which was experiencing chaos and division. In general, the Islamization carried out by traders through trade may be described as follows: at first, they came to trade centers, and then some of them resided, either temporarily or permanently. Gradually their place of residence developed into a village. The village of Muslim traders from foreign countries is called Pekojan.
2. Marriage Channels. Marriage is one of the most convenient ways to convert to Islam. Because the marriage link is both an inner and outer bond, a place for two persons to find harmony. The two individuals, specifically the husband and wife, create the family, which is at the heart of society. In this example, it refers to the establishment of a Muslim community. Islamization also occurs through marriage, specifically between traders or merchants and indigenous women. This positive relationship is occasionally maintained through marriages between indigenous women's daughters and Islamic traders. A Muslim is born as a result of this marriage. Economically speaking, Muslim traders enjoyed a higher social rank than the majority of indigenous people, which attracted indigenous women, particularly the daughters of nobles, to marry these merchants. They are Muslims prior to marriage. Their surroundings becomes more expansive once they produce progeny. Finally, communities, districts, and Muslim kingdoms existed.
3. The Sufism Channel. Sufism is a major conduit for Islamization. Sufism is a category that works and shapes the Indonesian people's social life, as evidenced by writings from the 13th to the 18th century. It is inextricably linked to Islam's spread in Indonesia. Sufism specialists in this situation live simply; they always strive to live the lives of their people and to coexist within their culture. Sufism professionals are typically skilled at curing diseases and other ailments. Sufism's approach, namely the process of Islamization through the teaching of theosophy and the incorporation of cultural values and even existing religion teachings, including Hinduism, into Islamic teachings, is first codified with Islamic values to make them understandable and acceptable. Sufism scholars Hamzah Fansuri in Aceh, Syeh Lemah Abang in Java, and Sunan Pangung in Java all issued instructions that were akin to the pre-Islamic Indonesian thinking. Mystical teachings of this nature are continuously evolving in the nineteenth century, and even into the twentieth century.
4. Educational Channels. Islamization was aided significantly by ulama, religious teachers, and rulers. They propagated Islam through education, specifically by establishing Islamic boarding schools where students were taught Islam. Religious professors, kyai, or ulama, prepare the Islamic boarding school. They would return to their respective villages or villages after studying religious information from numerous books to become religious leaders, becoming kyai who organize pesantren again. The more renowned the kyai who instructs, the more prominent the pesantren, and its radius of impact will expand even further.
5. Art Channel Islamization channels through building art, sculpture or carving, dance, music, and literary arts. For example, the art of this building can be seen in the ancient mosque of Demak, Sendang Duwur Agung Kasepuhan in Cirebon, the Great Mosque of Banten, Baiturrahman in Aceh, Ternate, and so on. Another example in art is puppet shows, which are

popular with the public. Through the wayang stories, Islamic teachings are inserted. Gamelan art can also invite the public to see the performance. Furthermore, Islamic religious da'wah was held.

6. Political Channels. The king's power exerts a tremendous influence on Islamization. When a ruler converts to Islam, his subjects will follow suit. The populace exhibits a high level of obedience, and the monarch, as a role model, even serves as an example for his subjects. For example, in South Sulawesi and Maluku, the majority of people converted to Islam after the king did. The king's political clout significantly aided in the propagation of Islam in this region.

Hadrah Tradition

According to Rosijani Arbie (2011) in his journal entitled Hadrah in the multicultural Jaton community in Minahasa, North Sulawesi is forming national character. The terms Hadrah and Hadi come from the same Arabic language, which means "present" or hadlir. Haldir in question is how we, as servants of God, can feel the presence of God within us. In another sense, Hadrah in Arabic is the term given to the collective ritual sunnah performed by Sufis. Ordinary Hadrah is most often held on the Thursday night after the evening prayer, the Friday after, or Sunday night.

Hadrah incorporates a variety of modes of dhikr (remembrance), including sermons, group studies, and reading the Koran and other holy texts (specific holy texts in Sufi orders (tarekat), known as Hizb and Wird, namely religious, poetic chants centered on praise and supplication to Allah, religious advice, praising the Prophet, and requests for mediation (inshad dini or madih—the latter term refers to "test (there is none worthy of worship but Allah). The rhythmic reading of names and the singing of religious poetry are frequently performed in tandem. Conservative Sufis do not utilize instruments, except for the Daf (drum frame), which is another commandment that requires instrumentation. In Arabic, the phrase translates as "presence." Sufi group rites are primarily conducted in the Arab world and a few non-Muslim Arab nations such as Indonesia and Malaysia under this name. Hadrah Sufism is sometimes referred to in Turkish as Devran, and it is a characteristic of the khalwati, syadzili, qadiri, and rifa'i orders throughout Turkey and the Balkans (Khuzairoh, 2021).

In the Big Indonesian Dictionary (1994), Hadrah is also defined as singing (Arabic) accompanied by a tambourine. Hadrah can also be said to be a folk song. What is meant by folk song here is one of the folklore genres consisting of words and songs that are circulated orally among members of a particular community collective, in traditional form and have many variants (Danandjaja, 1994). Based on Nasudin's research (2019), Hadrah art is a traditional musical art that has existed for a very long time and is in great demand by the public, especially among teenagers, both education level and not. In this thesis, Nasrudin discusses that this Hadrah art is usually done to read the Prophet's birthday, pray, and accompany the bride and groom.

In Indonesia, around the 13th century Hijri, a great cleric from Yemen named Habib Ali bin Muhammad bin Husain al-Habsyi (1259-1333/1839-1913M), came to his homeland on a mission to preach Islam. In addition, he also brought an Arabic art in the form of reading shalawat accompanied by a tambourine in the style of Habsyi or what is known today as Hadrah, by establishing a prayer meeting and praises to the Prophet as a means of mahabbah (love) to the Prophet Muhammad (Rody, 2018).

After some time, the majlis spread to all corners of the region, especially Banjar Masin, Kalimantan, and Java. He, Habib Ali bin Muhammad bin Husain Al-Habsyi also wrote a book entitled "Simthu Al-Durar," which contains the story of the journey of life from before birth to the death of the Prophet Muhammad. It also includes reading blessings and madaih (praises) to the Prophet. In commemorating the birthday of the Prophet Muhammad SAW, the book is often read and accompanied by hadrah musical instruments. So, until now, even this art has been attached to the community, especially prayer lovers, and as the existence of Islamic cultural art that must always be maintained and developed (Husniyah & Susanto, 2020).

The function of hadrah art is to calm the human mind and improve human nature. In addition, as a means of manifestation or encouragement in improving morality and spirituality in life. In addition, hadrah can function as a means or tool for dhikr, a manifestation, and form of gratitude to Allah SWT for the blessings he has given to his servants. Hadrah is an Islamic art in which there are religious values that influence the spirituality of the hadrah. Islam has a powerful influence on Indonesian culture in the social and state fields. The elements regarding justice, adab, people, wisdom, deliberation, or the scholars call it an "s al-hikmah al-mashurah, "wisdom is deliberation.

Hadrah Tradition as a Media of Communication and Social Interaction in Maluku

Islamic traders from Arab, Indian and Chinese countries brought Islam to the northern Maluku Islands. It has been found that Maluku inhabitants, particularly those living in commerce cities like Banda, Hitu, and Ternate, utilized Arabic script (Malay Arabic) in certain historical manuscripts that have been lost. All of this suggests that they were familiar with Arabic calligraphy

and had used it in various forms of correspondence. Indeed, Arabic numerals have been utilized in a variety of commerce transactions.

For the most part, migrants and Arabs excel at forging bonds with the Maluku people. Without Maluku's people's understanding, the image of Islam and Arabic has begun to spread. A majority of the assimilation movements were based on trade and religious education. Arabs and Moluccans are so muddled together that it's nearly impossible to tell them apart. This mindset has developed due to ongoing trade politics (Murod, 2011).

Hadrah is a custom that is still alive and well today. The Maluku people have a unique ritual known as 'Hadrah,' in which they commemorate Islamic holidays, weddings, circumcisions, and other religious rites. Muslims in Hadrah gathered to worship Prophet Muhammad SAW with a tambourine in the village, followed by parents, youths, and even toddlers dancing and shouting prayers to his best buddy.

Sheikh Abdul Qadir Jailani's Hadrah is Islamic culture. Each location has its own unique Hadrah tradition. When it comes to participating in Hadrah, participants' spirits can be lifted by this diversity. At the end of Eid al-Fitr, the Hadrah ritual is a way to show respect and thanks for the local community's ancestors. So, until the activity is completed, parents and children cannot leave the village. However, educating the younger generation and children about the true meaning of Hadrah is a critical task.

As a result, the Maluku people continue to value the Hadrah tradition as a vital component of communal life. Thus, various good outcomes were obtained in this study as a result of the Maluku Islands Hadrah becoming social sanctions, including:

1. Hadrah members bring the person in question to the seashore to be bathed together when the community is not involved. There is no reason for this to happen again, but it has a significant social impact. Since the commencement of their Hadrah, the community has abided by this rule.
2. The holy month of Ramadan culminates with Eid al-Fitr, when Muslims are obligated to fast for seven days. If Hadrah is missed, seven days of fasting are recommended. Ma'rifat is said to have descended on the seventh day. Those who don't observe Hadrah on Eid al-Adha should fast for three days to make 40 days equal to a human year. In the present day, this ritual continues to be practiced.
3. Attendance is a crucial self-discipline tool since it ensures that the tasks listed above are completed on time, for example, starting at 7:00 a.m. and continuing until they are completed.
4. Maren, the Maluku word for "togetherness," is a critical component of the Maluku concept of Hadrah (cooperation). Hadrah can reconcile social issues that are founded in local customs.

In light of this, we can see that Hadrah culture is a culture that places a high value on Islamic values. It serves as a tool for developing human character and helping people deal effectively with both the now and the hereafter. All of this demonstrates that the Hadra culture's existence indicates the development of human qualities such as obedience, a constant awareness of the goodness of God, and a desire to grow closer to the Creator. To benefit himself, others, the country, and the state. As a result of this hadra culture's application, a sense of unity, unity, mutual understanding, and a sense of solidarity, which humans recognize that togetherness is essential in life and hence the birth of human beings, can be seen in this regard as well. People with high character, i.e., those who are constantly kind to others, work together to build a fair and wealthy society.

CONCLUSION

Maluku is well-known for more than only its spice production. However, the arduous work of missionaries in teaching the Qur'an to people who had joined Islam during the early days of Islam in Maluku could not be separated from the development of Islam in Maluku. For Eid al-Fitr and Eid al-Adha, as well as other religious events, Hadrah is a unique custom that is observed by the Muslim community to memorialize the splendor of Islam on these occasions. Children and adults alike danced and sang in Hadrah to the accompaniment of music (tambourine) after a community meeting in and around the hamlet. They were joined by their best friend, Prophet Muhammad SAW, in Hadrah. Maluku people's Hadrah tradition, which is rooted in their culture, symbolizes the ideals of discipline, togetherness, kinship, and cooperation, and it can serve as a vehicle for interaction and the resolution of social issues that frequently arise in local communities. Also seen in the implementation of this hadra culture, in which the players must be united with one another in order to create a sense of togetherness, unity and mutual understanding as well as a sense of solidarity, which in the end leads to humans realizing that they require one another in order to survive, resulting in the birth of human beings. Quality humans, that is, humans who are constantly kind to others, assist one another in understanding.

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